

Social Media and Youth's Responsiveness to the 2023 Electoral Process in Rivers State

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Abstract

The study investigated the responsiveness of youths in Rivers state to social media campaigns in the 2023 general elections in Nigeria. The objectives were to evaluate the level of youths' engagement on social media and see how such level of engagement influences the youths' decision in terms of the electoral process. The study was anchored on the social learning theory. The study adopted the survey research design. The population of the study consisted of youths of Rivers State with a sample of 350 respondents. A combination of quota and convenience sampling technique was used to elicit information from the respondents using the questionnaire as a basic tool. Data were analysed using the Weighted Mean Scores on a four point Likert Scale and a 2.5 decision rule. The study found that the level of youth engagement on the social media is relatively high. The study also found that the youths responded positively to social media campaign messages relating to the 2023 elections. It was, therefore, concluded that social media played an effective role in enhancing and improving the political behaviour of youths towards the electoral processes. The study recommended that the government, political institutions and candidate of elections should maximise the tool of the social media in increasing and sustaining their followership and support in coming elections.

Keywords: Elections, Youths, Social Media, Responsiveness, Influence, Rivers State

Introduction

Politics is not new to Nigeria and over the years, the activities of politicians, in their quest for power, can best be described as desperate attempt at staying in power. The attitudes of politicians in Nigeria have made the people to disbelieve their intention thereby creating a difficult task in convincing the people to be part of the political

process. Amadi (2017) describes Nigerian politicians as persons moved by mere personal desire to occupy positions of authority without well thought out blueprint of their intendment. Elections in Nigeria have, therefore, become a very delicate and sensitive event in Nigerian history with each election circle accounting for series of human infractions. The 2023 election circle was one election that was keenly contested, drawing participation from different strata of the society, especially the youths. This is against a backdrop of one of the most challenging economic realities in Nigeria, prevalence of divisive national politics, persistent and rising insecurity, widespread corruption and a general sense of dissatisfaction among Nigerians. Most people were swayed into believing that either their votes will not count or that the election results would have been prepared even before voting actually commenced. But one thing that stood out during the electioneering process was the utilisation of social media as a veritable tool for mobilisation by both the ruling party (All Progressives Congress, APC) and the opposition political parties that participated in the elections.

Every eligible candidate understood that the support from the younger population (youths) will provide them with higher chances of victory under fair and acceptable circumstances and utilising every opportunity to earn their trust and engagements will be very instrumental to their success. And so they have moved the trend from using the conventional media to the new or social media to present their strong reasons, sample their portfolio, make their promises and propaganda towards the elections in order to attempt to influence decision making process. Social media are and will remain effective in being able to reach out to the young people of the country. These youths will only flow with what appeals to their taste and their needs. Any candidate aspiring for any political office that seeks to gain the patronage of these youths must have gained visibility and prominence on the social media first before even proceeding to the physical campaign. Social media to a very large extent have the ability to coordinate thoughts, thought patterns, influence decisions, actions and choices and the general elections are no exceptions. This study was, therefore, conceived to investigate the responsiveness of youths to social media electoral campaigns in Rivers State during the 2023 elections.

Statement of the Problem

The pervasiveness of the social media has made it a game changer in every sphere of national life. Despite the fact that the youths constitute more than half of the population in Nigeria, young people often tend to find themselves marginalised from mainstream politics and decision making. They struggle to gain the respect of public officials and are seen as lacking the skills and experience to engage in politics and governance, such that it leads to positive changes in the society. This exclusion, coupled with limited educational and economic opportunities, has left many youths idle and frustrated with the established order, thereby making them potential tools in the hands of the agents of destruction.

Due to the high cost of nomination forms by established political parties, the youths often turn to odd jobs during elections. Some vulnerable youths, resort to ballot snatching, violence, and killing that has transformed Nigerian elections into a battle

scenario. The people who perpetrate these nefarious acts receive little compensation, and they are usually abandoned after each election.

The need for change threw up the social media challenge where the youths had to be actively involved in the political campaigns to sell their preferred candidates to the people. Many a youth were engaged to manage social media handles of politicians while others served as influencers. In Rivers State, the media aide portfolio was further expanded to include a social media assistant that will be responsible for disseminating information and responding to enquiry on behalf of their principal. In fact, the social media aide configuration earned the nomenclature of data boys within the Nigerian political spectrum. How the data boys were able to influence the outcome of the 2023 election remains to be known, hence this inquest.

Objectives of the Study

This study sought to:

1. Determine the level of social media engagement by the youths during the 2023 elections.
2. Evaluate the degree of responsiveness of the youths to social media campaign messages in the 2023 elections.
3. Ascertain how Social media campaign influenced the youths' choices of the candidates.

Theoretical Framework

Social Learning Theory

Anaeto, Onabanjo & Osifeso (2008) reported that the history of the social learning theory can be traced to a psychologist, Albert Bandura who studied human behaviour in 1977. He is most likely known for his Bobo Doll study. Bandura had children watch adults model positive and negative behaviour towards a toy balloon resembling a clown. In some cases, the adults were aggressive and violently beat the doll. After observing this footage, the children were given hammers and asked to interact with the doll. Most children who witnessed the aggressive behaviour towards the doll also acted violently towards it, while most children who witnessed positive, non-aggressive behaviour responded less aggressively. Bandura then concluded that the children learned their social behaviour through observation. Children pay attention to these models and encode their behaviour, at a later time, they may imitate or copy the behaviour they observed. This study acted as the basis for Bandura's theory. The social learning theory is still commonly used in social psychology today and relates with other behaviourist theories such as nature versus nature, symbolic interaction, situated learning, reinforcement learning and social development.

Social learning theory is the study of learned behaviour through the observation, modeling and imitating of new behaviors that are reinforced by other people or models. As a result, new behaviours either continue or cease depending on how they are reinforced or rewarded in the social environment (Fitzgibbons, 2019).

When it comes to political campaigns, the social learning theory can help us understand how individuals acquire and shape their political belief, attitudes and behaviour based on the behaviour of others they observed during campaigns. Political campaigns often involve various forms of communication such as speeches, debates, advertisements, and social media campaigns. Through these channels, candidates and their supporters try to influence the opinions and behaviours of voters. According to social learning theory, individuals observe and pay attention to actions and messages of political candidates and overtime may choose to copy or imitate them if they feel quite interested in political activities. If individuals see political figures or supporters engaging in certain behaviour, expressing particular beliefs, or promoting specific policies, they may be likely to adopt or imitate those forms of behaviour. This process of observational learning can influence voter preferences and political participation in the electoral processes. By analysing the dynamics of social learning, political campaigns can strategically design their messages, imagery, and campaign activities to shape voter's perceptions and behaviours.

Conceptual Review

New Media

The new media have created an avenue for political parties to reach a larger audience with ease and less stress. The new media are simply channels for the dissemination of information. Media serve as the link between the sender and receiver of information. Media are varied and dependent on the communication type. The word 'media' evokes a picture of multiple channels of communication, especially the mass media, in the heart of non-communication experts. What can be termed as media goes beyond the radio, television, newspapers etc. it comprises all forms of channels that messages can pass through, whatever the content, from one point to the other.

The new media are an off shoot of unending technological innovations by inventors in the information and communication technology space. These inventors have gone beyond the limits to ensure that man have several choices in terms of communicating along distant planes. Telephone or e-mail would have been the only means of communication across the distance technologically but more channels keep coming up daily, leaving man with the confusion of choosing the appropriate channel of communication backed by technology. Bolade (2017) defined the new media as means of mass communication using digital technologies such as the internet. He noted that the ease of communication and business interaction, serving as all-in-one means of digital communication, wireless networking and the ease to carry and manage it are some of the reason people tend to prefer the new media. Users of new media have almost immediate access to information. They also enjoy the liberty of contributing and interacting with whatever information they choose to consume. They do this by commenting, sharing and discussing a wide variety of subjects, often times with little or no moderation.

Interactivity is the live wire of the new media. This means that political parties deploying the new media can now have the opportunity of having direct feedback from

the people. According to Okedi (2021), deploying the new media in organisational management and operations, makes the global communication nexus a reality. New media, therefore, have the following advantages:

- a. It is fast and convenient because of its speed owing to upgrade of communication infrastructure globally.
- b. It breaks the barriers of time and space. Social media contents go viral and are not restricted by time or space. In fact, social media contents can come in the form of live feeds on the information super highway.
- c. It breaks human protocols and procedures. Social media has rendered some known human communication infrastructure like the post office and courier services. These outlets now carry other forms of good and services other than recent information. In fact, the invention of artificial intelligence, the process of information generation and sharing has undergone a serious revolution.
- d. It serves as a record keeping mechanism. The records of the communication process are very traceable overtime.
- e. There are checks and balances. The social media platforms have their checking mechanism that keeps the space safe for all users. It is called community standards and defaulters are punished accordingly.
- f. It makes communication more specific. Everyone operates with a tag and identifying the source of the message is easy.
- g. It makes organisational operations timeless and limitless.
- h. It is very cost effective. Multiple sources can be reached simultaneously within a given time.
- i. It makes an organisation more responsive to the needs of their stakeholders.

Conversely, deploying new media in an organisation comes with its own headaches in the following ways:

- i. Cost of maintenance of communication infrastructure will go up periodically.
- ii. Cost of training the employees will add to organisational budget.
- iii. There are incidences of network interruptions which might hamper organisational operations.
- iv. There are industrial hazards associated with the communication infrastructure.
- v. Incidents of hackers hijacking organisational communication platforms persist.
- vi. Government policies can interfere organisational operations as in the case of Twitter Ban.
- vii. It creates over-dependence on technology to deliver organisational goals.

Features of New Media

The new media according to Bolade (2017), have the following features that drive users:

Direct Access: The new media grants direct access to target audience, removing red-tape and other forms of bureaucratic bottlenecks from the conversation between the organisation and its target audience. This is a tool for organisational planning because it removes irrelevant protocols in the information collection and dissemination process.

Defies Time and Space: The barriers of time are removed because of the simultaneity of sending and receiving messages on the new media platforms. The barriers of distance are also removed as there is no restriction as to who should be on the platform based on geography.

User-Generated Content: The new media allow users to generate content and also empowers them to share information created by other users, thus increasing the reach of information.

Engendering Conversations: The new media engenders conversation between people, sometimes, with people who might never have had the opportunity to meet or ever converse. This is because the barriers of time and space have been conquered. Again, interest is kindled by the flexibility in the communication process.

Low Access Cost: Accessing the new media is relatively cheaper and convenient for its users. It has made communicating with more people possible because it now takes less effort to communicate when compared with the practice of using mass media channels like television, radio or newspapers. Communicating on the new media personalises communication to the extent that the communicators feel a sense of connection between them.

Social Media and Political Campaigns in 2023 Elections

The number of active social media users in Nigeria according to the National Bureau of Statistics had risen from twenty seven (27) million in 2019, to thirty six (36) million ahead of the 2023 elections. Given the challenge of the prevailing misinformation and disinformation on social media platforms and the way such disinformation can permeate into the media more generally, political parties had to latch on to the social media to reach out to the electorates. In fact, there was practically no political party in Nigeria that did not utilise the social media to reach the electorates. Consequently, the citizenry were almost confused with the *infoglut* entrenching pre-existing divides based on ethnicity and religion, especially as misinformation, a deliberate sharing of information with the intent to cause harm, that characterised the elections. Cross-platforms were created to counter information from perceived political enemies.

One prominent feature of the 2023 election was the participation of the *Obidients* who were rooting for the presidential candidate of the Labour party, Mr. Peter Obi. The

Obidients were practically netizens as most of their communication was online including meetings and other forms of mobilization. The Obidients put pressure on the electoral umpire in Nigeria by streaming election results from various wards online and reporting incidents of infractions by the participants in the process. This brought about a sharp divide between the political parties and their supporters which has persisted till date. Nigeria's digital ecosystem was reshaped as screen grabs or contents from one platform could be shared across others, broadening the reach beyond the number of direct users. Content also moves from online forums into offline spaces, with soldiers of mouth spreading online corner through street talks, in motor parks and at newspaper stands.

The disinformation ecosystem created lucrative opportunities, particularly for the youths to exploit. Some of the most prominent political influencers on social media, who are hired by political parties or individual candidate, earn up to Five Hundred Thousand (500,000) Naira per month whilst those with smaller followings earned less. There was a plethora of media influencers who were eager to feed the hungry audience with juicy information about their preferred candidates for the elections.

In previous elections, text and pictures were dominant but in 2023, the emphasis was more on the real time live streaming of audio and video content on social media platforms. One of the innovations was the organisation of political song challenges. For all social media platform, the line between the online and the offline remains blurred. But social media more regularly, serves as a source of content inspiration from the, mainstream media. It is common to find issues trending on Twitter being discussed on morning or evening debate shows, as this is what the audience is looking to hear. In that sense, media houses are bringing the online into the conventional media and people's homes. And they invite so-called political consultants and experts into their studios, they invite disinformation specialists. These individuals are often paid to peddle half-truths, promote conspiracy theories or attempt to legitimise false information flowing online (Ibrahim, 2023).

Empirical Review

Ibanga, Arugu & Bolade (2023) found that the government of late President Mohammadu Buhari utilised the Twitter (now X), to reach out to the people on security, corruption, education and other issues of governance. This implies that social media usage is not limited to youths, the government is beginning to take interest in utilising the social media because of its ability to reach more persons especially the youths. The utilisation of social media is expanding by the day and will continue for years to come especially with the introduction of artificial intelligence.

Ugondo, Ciboh & Bo (2023) were of the view that public service broadcasting was being politically and economically influenced other than being driven by public interest. This made mainstream media outlets less independent and partial in their attention and intentions of media operators on public issues especially elections. According to them, "during the electioneering, public service broadcasting do focus predominantly on a narrowly determined economic rights of access to broadcast media and on the ruling party or ownership to broadcast networks... the continuation of

commercialisation of access and the prioritisation of incumbent and other key political candidates' rights over public interest and civil rights has restricted access to public media stations." The trio further warned that the broadcast media must be allowed to serve the people independently by ensuring the equal rights of citizens or face extinction.

Nyekwere, Okoro & Azubuike (2014) in their study entitled "An assessment of the use of social media as advertising vehicles in Nigeria: A study of Facebook and Twitter" examined the growing impact of the social media on businesses in Nigeria. The study revealed that since the introduction of Facebook and Twitter, a growing number of commercial organisations have been embracing them as part of their marketing strategy, noting that they have seemingly discovered the potential of the social media in promoting customer relations and increasing product patronage. The study concluded that social media advertising is an evolving trend in marketing, especially in Nigeria. It is no longer a question of whether a business organisation/entrepreneur should have a marketing presence on social media but a dedicated Facebook and Twitter presence is expedient to them to leverage on the advantages these media provided for both ordinary users and those using them for marketing purposes.

Another study by Akinola & Okunade (2016) evaluated the use of the internet as a medium for marketing and advertising messages in Nigeria. The study took cognizance of the increase in active Internet subsequent (GSM) in Nigeria, vis-a-viz the popularity of an acceptance of the internet as a medium for communicating marketing and advertising messages. The findings had revealed that young people between the ages of 18 to 45 years form the substantial majority of internet users in Nigeria. This buttresses the fact that the use of the internet would have increased in Nigeria but it appears that many Nigerians still see it as a social fad; they see it from the point of view socialising, research and educational purposes, hence their preference for Facebook and Google websites.

Again, Chukwu & Uzoma (2014) examined "the impact of social media networks on consumer patronage in Nigeria: A study of Jumia and Konga Nigeria Limited." The study underscored the burgeoning posture of the social media in the Nigeria online marketing industry. A cursory look at indigenous online marketing companies like Jumia and Konga Nigeria Limited in relation to what levels of patronage they have enjoyed via the social media. The study had revealed that in spite of differences in the perception of consumers about social media marketing, they tend to patronise online retailers very significantly.

Methodology

The study adopted a survey design. A sample of 350 respondents was determined from the 2024 projected population of over three million (3,817,866) youths in Rivers State using the Krejcie & Morgan (1970) table. The combination of convenience and availability sample technique was deployed to reach target population. The questionnaire was used to collect data from the respondents with the aid of three research assistants considering the number of local government to be covered which was twenty three. Data were analysed using the Weighted Mean Scores on a four point Likert Scale with a 2.5 decision rule.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1: Level of Social Media Engagement of Youths during the 2023 Elections

Level of Social Media Engagement of Youths during the 2023 Elections	SA	A	D	SD	WMS	Decision
Youths in Rivers State were not keen on social media campaign messages during the 2023 elections	-	7 (14)	231 (462)	112 (112)	1.96	Disagreed
Few youths were involved in viewing social media campaign messages during the 2023 elections	-	-	203 (406)	147 (147)	1.58	Disagreed
Majority of the youths in Rivers State depended on social media campaign messages in 2023 elections	301 (1204)	35 (105)	7 (14)	7 (7)	3.8	Agreed

The table above shows that majority of the youths in Rivers State depended and heavily, on social media campaign messages during the 2023 election circle. This is because a lot of youths are connected through the internet on social media platforms.

Table 2: Degree of Responsiveness of the Youths to Social Media Campaign Messages in the 2023 Elections

Degree of Responsiveness of the Youths to Social Media Campaign Messages in the 2023 Elections	SA	A	D	SD	WMS	Decision
Social media campaign messages did not influence my voting decision	7 (28)	91 (273)	224 (448)	28 (28)	2.22	Disagreed
Social media campaign messages did influence my voting decision	91 (364)	154 (462)	84 (168)	21 (21)	2.9	Agreed
Social media campaign messages did not influence my choice of political party in the elections	112 (448)	98 (294)	38 (76)	7 (7)	2.36	Disagreed
Social media campaign messages did influence my choice of political for the election	56 (224)	175 (525)	77 (154)	42 (42)	2.7	Agreed

Social media campaigns has great influence on the participation of youths in 2023 elections 231 (924) 91 (273) 28 (56) - 3.58 Agreed

The table above shows that social media campaigns had a profound influence on the participation of youths in the 2023 elections by influencing their choice of political party and their voting decision eventually. It means that social media messages can be a deal breaker in mobilising the youths in the electoral process. Social media makes information readily available for those that seek to know.

Table 3: Social Media Campaign Influence on the Youths’ Choices of the Candidates

Social Media Campaign Influence on the Youths’ Choices of the Candidates	SA	A	D	SD	WMS	Decision
Identification of candidates by name	189 (756)	147 (441)	14 (28)	-	3.5	Agreed
Identification of political parties	14 (56)	77 (231)	238 (476)	21 (21)	2.24	Disagreed
Identification of party ideology	14 (56)	77 (231)	238 (476)	21 (21)	2.24	Disagreed
Credible information about the elections schedules	56 (224)	154 (462)	98 (196)	42 (42)	2.64	Agreed

The table above shows that it was through social media campaigns that the youths identified the various candidates by name and also got credible information about the schedule for the elections.

Discussion of Findings

The result showed that majority of the youths in Rivers State depended and heavily, on social media campaign messages during the 2023 election circle. This is because a lot of youths are connected through the internet on social media platforms. Many studies have focused on how humans use the social media to communicate and carry out other communication-related activities with the convenience of time. But there are little researches as to how organisations have managed to keep a clean slate operationally by deploying the new media in implementing their goals and objectives within society using limited human interface. For some authors, the new media is a game changer in the realm of organisational communication while others argue that “the new media has created new problems for organisations because of the fluidity of getting false or unsubstantiated information across the cyber space for mass consumption” (Nkwocha, 2016, p. 157).

The fact that the new media have greatly influenced the manner of socio-cultural, socio-economic, socio-religious cum socio-linguistic interactions in the world is no longer a matter for debate. The term has blossomed to encompass different aspects of computing and technological advancements in communication. Few years back, the concept of ‘media’ denoted only the print and broadcast media. But today, a lot has

changed and will continue to change with limitless possibilities being churned out through technological innovations in information and communication technology. The new media have brought about multi-dimensional variations in the world of communication. It has exceeded limitations and borders, enhanced immediacy in communication reception and responses, shrunken the world into a global village and enriched the means of reaching out to a very enormous heterogeneous audience (Lister, Dovey, Giddings, Grant & Kelly, 2009).

The result further showed that social media campaigns had a profound influence on the participation of youths in the 2023 elections by influencing their choice of political party and their voting decision eventually. It means that social media messages can be a deal breaker in mobilising the youths in the electoral process. Social media makes information readily available for those that seek to know. This finding has reechoed the treatise by Halbrooks (2016) who averred that “today, a candidate can bypass broadcast and print media to reach his potential voters through social media. A Facebook page can show he has 20,000 fans, offer his entire news conference and most importantly, allow him a totally unfiltered way to speak...A wise candidate however, should realise that social media is a tool, but it has yet to replace the value of getting his face on the front page of the paper or on the evening newscast. This finding also tallies with the conclusions of Woluchem (2020) that new media’s role in fostering a more active electorate is perhaps their most consequential implication for campaigns. She further submits that voters use new media to participate in campaigns in traditional and novel ways.

The findings further showed that it was through social media campaigns that the youths identified the various candidates by name and also got credible information about the schedule for the elections. The social media has developed so much that it incorporates all that the print and electronic media do and more. The social media therefore has a lot more influence than the duo of television and radio combined as has been indicated by respondents. This is also the position of (Okogbule, 2017) who opines that you never know what might change someone’s mind. Something like an image, as we have seen time and time again, can change the world....voters will go online to meet other likeminded people and express their views, which are often, but not always too entrenched to be swayed by a single Facebook post.

Okogbule (2017, p. 13) who notes that ‘technology has facilitated social interaction through the mass media, via radio, television, newspapers, and now the useful but increasingly abused, Internet. Social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Whatsapp and Instagram are now ubiquitous and they almost dictate our lives and activities for good or bad.’ Amadi (2017) in support of media influence in polls opines that declining partisanship, proliferation of media sources and the professionalisation of campaign communications in most electoral democracies suggest that there is potential for the media to have a significant influence in engaging citizens in the election and shaping party and candidate preferences.

Nwokah (2018), however, is of the view that campaign effects tend to be a comparatively weak force, whose effects can be deflected, diluted and diffused by

stronger forces such as bedrock political values associated with class, religion, age, gender and education, as well as social networks and discussions, distrust of the mass media and personal knowledge and experience. As at today, man has moved from speech to speed in his daily transactions. It is no longer impossible to get served as a client on the go without first visiting the organisation in its official quarters. Several organisations have migrated their office online and are fully virtual in their operations. In fact, Nigeria was rated among the top twenty countries with highest members of Internet users in the world (Nwokah, 2018).

Conclusion and Recommendations

Social media have come to stay as part of societal media architecture. The gatekeeping protocols birthed by regulatory control of both the print and electronic media makes it impossible for certain forms of societal content to find their way into the conventional media. But for the social media, the control is very minimal and the interactivity cum reach, global when compared to the reach of conventional media. It therefore makes more economic sense for the youths to choose the social media since it gives them greater control of their daily conversations. Political parties spend less when they utilise the social media as a tool for information dissemination and the platforms gives them greater convergence and reach. With these, social media do not only hold sway as the preferred channel of choice, it also ranks as one of the most efficient means of information dissemination. The ability of the youths of Rivers State to engage with political actors on social media made them more responsive to the electoral process, thereby conferring legitimacy on the elections. The cases of voter apathy was minimised to the extent that the youths saw the need to fulfill their civil obligations instead of staying aloof as was the case in previous election years.

Organisations are, therefore, encouraged to overlook the vagaries of perceived fake news emanating from the social media and utilise its ubiquity for their benefit. The youths are easier to reach through the social media and their population and activeness cannot be ignored by any organisation. The study further recommends that the government, political institutions and candidates of elections should maximise the tool of the social media in increasing and sustaining their followership and support in coming elections.

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